

Research

Study on Critical Speed Behavior of Rotating Machinery

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Received: 3 October 2025

Accepted: 7 October 2025

Published Online: 8 October 2025

***Correspondence:**Department, University, Address, City,
Post Code, Country**How to cite this article:**

Md Bayjid Maharaj, Guangfu Bin (2025). Study on Critical Speed Behavior of Rotating Machinery North American Academic Research, 8(10), 29-43. doi:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17295467>

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Abstract

The vibration issues of turbo machinery rotors such as centrifugal compressors, centrifugal pumps, steam turbines, and aviation engines are directly related to the safety of the equipment. As turbo machinery continuously seeks higher efficiency, the inevitable trend in rotor structure development is high-speed operation and multi-stage impellers. Due to factors like material inhomogeneity of the rotor, machining and assembly deviations, and changes in environmental parameters during operation, rotors with blades will inevitably develop mass imbalances. Under high-speed and high-parameter operating conditions, this can lead to increased rotor vibration, seriously affecting the safe and stable operation of the machinery and becoming a technical problem that urgently needs analysis and resolution. The key points and basic methods of dynamic balancing technology were analyzed, and a rotor dynamic balancing experimental plan was designed. Using the influence coefficient method, a set of correction masses that are not orthogonal to the first N modal shapes can be obtained in one attempt. Experiments were conducted to validate the imbalance vibration characteristics of the rotor and to research dynamic balancing techniques. The experimental results showed that after dynamic balancing, the vibration of the rotor was significantly reduced, with a vibration reduction of up to 83.2% on Balancing Plane 1 and up to 75.4% on Balancing Plane 2.

Keywords: Rotor; Unbalance, vibration Characteristics; Finite Element Modeling; Turbo machinery

1. Introduction

Turbo machinery rotors play a key role in a variety of industrial applications, including energy generation, aviation, and refining Zeng et al. [1]. The ability to convert thermal energy into mechanical power is essential for the smooth operation of equipment such as centrifugal compressors, pumps, and steam turbines Pérez et al. [2]. However, these rotors are susceptible to vibration and mass unbalance issues due to factors including material heterogeneity, manufacturing defects, and operational stresses Lu et al. [3]. These vibrations can lead to catastrophic failures, excessive wear and tear, noise, and performance degradation Liu et al. [4]. Therefore, rotor dynamics must be carefully analyzed and managed to ensure mechanical stability and reliability Pellegrini et al. [5]. As the demand for increased efficiency in turbo machinery grows, rotors are being designed for higher operating speeds and complex multi-stage configurations Yang et al. [6]. These advancements necessitate corresponding improvements in energetic balancing methods to mitigate the detrimental effects of unbalance-induced vibrations Nanfei et al. [7]. The complex dynamics associated with advanced rotor systems require sophisticated approaches, including constrained optimization techniques and modular balancing strategies, for which traditional balancing methods are often inadequate Cui et al. [8]. Consequently, it has become critical to examine the interactions between rotor design, operating conditions, and

dynamic behavior to develop robust solutions to vibration issues Wu et al. [9]. The purpose of this review is to investigate the unbalanced vibration characteristics of multi-disk rotor machines through detailed finite element simulations and experimental tests Liao et al. [10]. By simulating various unbalance scenarios and conducting energetic balancing tests, this study aims to identify key factors influencing overall rotor performance while validating numerical models against experimental data. The results of this research are expected to make a valuable contribution to the understanding of rotor dynamics and facilitate the development of advanced balancing technologies to enhance the stability and reliability of turbo machinery in high-speed applications.

Nelson et al. [11,12] early published research ideas on modelling and solving nonlinear rotor systems are still instructive for present day rotor system research. Chen et al. [13] using finite element software combined with Lagrangian equations, established a nonlinear dynamics model for flexible rotor systems. Zhang et al. [14,15] focused on the significant impact of structural components such as supports and casings on the dynamic characteristics of the entire machine in aviation engines, studying the radial stiffness calculation methods for typical support structure components such as casing systems, elastic supports, and bearings, and their effects on the vibration response characteristics of rotor systems, and established a two-degree-of-freedom dynamics model for dual rotor systems. Wang et al. [16,17] combined finite element methods with fixed interface modal synthesis to establish a nonlinear dynamics model of the rotor system. Luo et al. [18], addressing the vibration response coupling phenomenon caused by intermediate bearings between dual rotor systems, derived the equations of motion for rotors and bearings and established an aviation engine dual rotor model considering the dynamics characteristics of rolling bearings and casings. Cavalca et al. [19] established a finite element model of the rotor system and reduced the degrees of freedom of the model using modal methods based on modal parameters such as generalized mass, damping ratio, and natural frequencies. Luo et al. [20] established a finite element model for a cantilevered combined rotor-support system, considering the local nonlinear support forces generated by the combined support and the coupling effects between the rotor and the combined support, derived a high-dimensional partial differential equation with local non linearity, and solved it using a combination of Newmark- β and Runge-Kutta methods. Hong et al. [25-27] studied the effects of the support position and support stiffness of high-speed flexible rotors on the stiffness, critical speed, and nonlinear vibration responses of rotor systems. Mao et al. [28] established a quasi-dynamic iterative finite element model for a thin-walled integrated squirrel-cage type flexible support-rolling bearing, analyzing the impact of the integrated flexible support structure on the internal load distribution and dynamic characteristics of rolling bearings. Guskov et al. [29] established a numerical model for dual rotors and studied the unbalance vibration response of the dual rotor system. Tiwari et al. [30] researched the impact of imbalance on the dynamic response characteristics of the rolling bearing-rigid rotor system. Zhang et al. [36] used genetic algorithms, particle swarm algorithms, and combined GA-PSO methods to comprehensively identify rotor system imbalances in terms of number, position, mass, and phase information. Liu et al. [37] proposed a method to analyze imbalances by controlling the response displacement of single-disk or multi-disk. Bin et al. [38,39] discovered that the harmonic components induced by the same phase combination of oil film bearing rotor imbalance were richer than those of the opposite phase combination.

These studies have yielded many valuable research findings in rotor system dynamics modeling, using methods such as concentrated mass and simplified supports to simplify the rotor system model, establishing rotor system equations and finite element models through finite element methods, transfer matrix methods, and others, providing a solid foundation for subsequent research. Much research has been done on the effects on the inherent properties and vibration responses of rotor systems and the vibration responses to rotor system imbalance, achieving many meaningful results, while studies on the impact of rotor vibration responses in turbo shaft engines are relatively fewer.

2. Research Strategy and Methodological Framework for Investigating Rotor Vibration Characteristics

2.1 Approach to Understanding Rotor Unbalance Characteristics

The research strategy used in this study is a systematic approach to investigate the unbalanced vibration characteristics of turbo machinery rotors. This method includes a summary of numerical simulations and experimental tests to verify the numerical concepts. This method provides a complete knowledge of the dynamic behavior of the rotor and its response to various unbalance events. The approach to the study is guided by the research question: "What is the effect of unbalance on the vibration characteristics of a turbo machinery rotor?" This problem is addressed through a series of numerical simulations and experimental evaluations that investigate the consequences of different unbalance scenarios on the rotor vibration response. This research method is designed to provide fundamental information about rotor behavior and reveal the key factors affecting rotor vibration characteristics.

To achieve this goal, research methods include a combination of theoretical and experimental strategies. Theoretical methods include the modification of a finite detail version of the rotor, which is used to simulate the vibration response under various unbalance conditions. This testing technique involves performing vibration measurements on a scaled-down version of the rotor. This is used to validate the numerical results and provide further insight into the behavior of the rotor. In addition, the research strategy includes a literature review to collect data on previous studies on turbine engine rotors and their vibration characteristics. This literature review provides valuable insight into the pitfalls studied and outlines the research approach for this trial. This assessment highlights the need for further research into the consequences of rotor unbalance in turbine machinery and identifies key areas for research. The global research strategy used in this review is designed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the unbalanced vibration characteristics of turbo machinery rotors. By combining numerical simulations with experimental tests and literature review, this study aims to discover the key factors that affect the rotor vibration response and provide valuable effects. The approach used in this study includes a combination of numerical simulation and experimental validation to investigate the unbalanced vibration characteristics of turbo machinery rotors. Numerical simulation is performed using the commercial software program ANSYS Mechanical. This program is used to simulate the vibration response of a rotor under multiple unbalance scenarios. Experimental tests include vibration measurements on a scale model of the rotor. This is used to verify the numerical effects and gain further insight into the behavior of the rotor.

In the numerical simulation, the rotor is modeled as a 3D model with limited detail with a hexahedron coefficient of 20 nodes. The properties of the fabric used are completely based on the actual material specifications of the rotor. The simulation system includes modeling, meshing, boundary conditions, loading tools and responses. Boundary conditions are designed to simulate reasonable operating conditions such as static loads, free disks and friction less bearings. Experimental control includes measurement of rotor scale model vibration using accelerometer and statistics collection system. The instrument view simulates the operating conditions of a turbo shaft engine rotor, while the accelerometer scales the vibration displacement and speed response. The recording system detects vibrations at different speeds and load conditions. The method adopted in this perspective is designed to provide accurate and reliable effects that can be used to capture the unbalanced vibration characteristics of mechanical turbine rotors. Using a combination of numerical simulation and experimental validation, we select the key factors that affect the rotor vibration response and aim to provide valuable insights into rotor behavior. The process adopted for this study consists of a number of steps designed to investigate the unbalanced vibration characteristics of mechanical turbine rotors. The system starts with modeling and meshing. This means developing a 3D finite element version of the rotor using the DyroBes software. Dyrobes is a comprehensive software tool designed for rotor dynamics analysis. The software provides robust features for rotor dynamic evaluation, vibration analysis, bearing performance assessment, and balancing calculations, all based on Finite Element Analysis principles.

Consequent boundary circumstances are performed to reenact sensible working circumstances, including a settled center, unfixed plate, and friction less orientation. Applying loads implies utilizing hundreds of lopsided characteristics to recreate particular awkward occasions. The reenactment strategy then includes deciding the uprooting and speed reaction employing a limited detail analysis. Experimental testing comprises performing vibration estimations on a scaled-down form of the rotor utilizing accelerometer and a fact-gathering framework. The test fix recreates operational circumstances, such as accelerometer, relocation degrees, and pace reactions. Data assessment incorporates measurable assessment utilizing program counting MATLAB or Exceed expectations to uncover patterns and designs in vibration reactions. The comes about are at that point compared with FEA reenactment comes about to confirm accuracy. The strategy utilized in this study is outlined to supply redress and solids that can be utilized to capture the unequal vibration characteristics of turbo machinery rotors. In this way, he seeks after the desire to find the key components affecting the behavior of the rotor.

This method combines a research attempt and numerical reconstruction to characterize the non-uniform vibration of a turbo machinery rotor. The procedure is divided into two different levels: limited component evaluation (FEA) and test testing.

2.2 Experimental Validation of Rotor Vibration Analysis

The FEA frame is calibrated by examining its interaction with the test reality of a scaled-down turbo shaft engine rotor frame. The validation methodology integrates the evaluation of vibration displacement and velocity characteristics between FEA entertainment and research measurements. By combining FEA reconstructions and

research tests, this observation controls a comprehensive understanding of the unequal vibration characteristics of turbo machinery rotors and their response to distributed imbalances.

3. Rotor Vibration Response and Balancing Method Evaluation

The forced vibration differential equation for a rotor system with imbalanced mass can be expressed as:

$$[M]\{\ddot{q}\} + ([C] + [G])\{\dot{q}\} + [K]\{q\} = \{f\} \quad (1)$$

Where, [M] is the mass matrix and symmetry matrix of the system; [C] It is a damping matrix, an asymmetric matrix; [G] It is a gyroscopic matrix, anti symmetric matrix; [K] Is the stiffness matrix; Ω is the angular velocity of the rotor. {q} To respond to the displacement vector of the system, it is generally determined by the lateral deformation values rx and ry, as well as the rotation angle θ_x and θ_y composition; {f} It is the centrifugal force acting on the system. The vibration response and centrifugal force can be respectively represented as:

$$\begin{aligned} \{q\} &= \{r\}e^{i\Omega t}e^{i\varphi} \\ \{f\} &= \{u\}e^{i\Omega t} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In equation (1), {r} and {u} represent the measured vibration response and unbalance, respectively. among φ Substituting equation ((2) into equation (5-1) for the system hysteresis angle yields:

$$([K] - \Omega^2[M] + i([C] + [G])\Omega)\{r\}e^{i\varphi} = \{u\} \quad (3)$$

Recorded as:

$$[A]^{-1}\{r\} = \{u\} \quad (4)$$

Here, [A] is the influence coefficient matrix, i.e:

$$[A] = ([K] - \Omega^2[M] + i([C] + [G])\Omega)^{-1}e^{-i\varphi} \quad (5)$$

From equation (5), it's clear that the influence coefficient matrix [A] is related to the mass, stiffness, damping, gyroscopic torque, and system lag angle of the turbomachinery system, and it is also a function of rotational speed. Currently, [A] can be obtained by applying trial weights on the balancing plane and measuring the imbalance response at specific measurement points. The residual vibration after balancing can be represented as:

$$\{r_{residual}\} = \{r_0\} + [A]\{p\} \quad (6)$$

In the above equation, {r₀} represents the original vibration vector. When {p} = -{u}, it indicates that the corrected mass is opposite to the original unbalance. If the residual vibration requirement after equilibrium is zero, equation (6) can be written as:

$$\{p\} = -[A]^{-1}\{r_0\} = -[a_{ij}]^{-1}\{r_0\} \quad (7)$$

Which

$$a_{ij} = (r_{ij} - r_{i0}) / w_i \quad (8)$$

In the formula mentioned, r_{ij} represents the vibration at the i th measurement point after adding a trial weight w_i on plane j, r_{i0} is the original vibration at the i th measurement point, and a_{ij} is the influence coefficient of the unit unbalance on plane j for the i th measurement point. It represents the vibration vector at a certain vibration measurement point caused by adding a unit mass (kg) on the rotor, placed in the zero-degree direction at a radius of 1 meter or a fixed radius. In dynamic balancing, the influence coefficient represents a constant relationship between the bearing vibration amplitude and phase measured with the same micrometer and the mass and direction of the added weight on the rotor, under specified bearings and speed. It is an inherent property of the rotor system. Therefore, the key to applying the influence coefficient method for the dynamic balancing of flexible rotors in turbo machinery is how to accurately obtain the influence coefficients of the added weight at various measurement points on the rotor.

From equation (8), it is clear that the influence coefficient method utilizes the linear relationship between correction quantities and measurements in a linear system, integrating mathematical methods with rotor balancing technology, thereby greatly facilitating the calculation of rotor and rotor balancing weights. It combines with rigid rotor balancing technology to become the rigid rotor influence coefficient balancing method; when combined with flexible rotor balancing technology, it becomes the flexible rotor influence coefficient balancing method. Since the balancing principle of rigid rotors is relatively simple, the rigid rotor influence coefficient balancing method is also more intuitive and straightforward. For flexible rotors, the imbalance is divided into two types: under rigid and flexible modes. The imbalance under rigid mode, at high speeds, generates unbalanced forces that, along with the bearing reaction forces, create a moment causing the rotor to bend and deform, thus altering the balance state under rigid mode. The imbalance under flexible mode occurs because the balance weights added under rigid mode differ significantly from the actual axial distribution of the rotor's imbalance. As the speed increases, internal moments formed by the

unbalanced forces on the cross-sections and the added balance weights cause the rotor to bend and deform, disrupting the rotor balance.

Therefore, to eliminate the unbalanced vibration faults of flexible rotors in turbo machinery like compressors, steam turbines, and gas turbines, it is crucial to combine the influence coefficient method with flexible rotor balancing technology effectively. This can reduce the number of starts and stops of the balancing unit and improve the rotor vibration level. The specific operation process must satisfy the following three technical points:

(1) Balance speed should not be limited to a single speed

Since the bending stiffness of the rotor and the bending moment acting on the rotor vary with speed, the size and direction of rotor deflection, i.e., the magnitude and direction of rotor unbalance, also change with speed. Ignoring this and using either the bearing reaction force zero balance weight calculation method or the least squares method will balance the flexible rotor using the rigid rotor influence coefficient method, ensuring satisfactory vibration only at the balance speed but not guaranteeing vibration at other speeds. Therefore, when using the influence coefficient method to balance flexible rotors in turbo machinery, it is necessary to solve the equation system, including vibrations at critical speeds sensitive to the rotor mode shape, in addition to working speed vibrations.

(2) Balance weights should not be orthogonal to the rotor mode shape

A real rotor typically exhibits multiple forms of unbalance simultaneously, often involving first, second, and third-order imbalances. Therefore, the bearing amplitude of a flexible rotor is generally the superposition of the first, second, and third-order unbalance vibrations, meaning the influence coefficients of a flexible rotor are the vector sum of each order mode shape's influence coefficients. To balance the vibration modes of a flexible rotor using the influence coefficient method, it is necessary to utilize the non-orthogonality of the balance weights to the mode shapes. This requires selecting the axial position of the weighting planes to achieve significant balancing effects under the corresponding mode shapes, and the number of weighting planes should not be less than the order of the highest mode shape of the rotor to be balanced.

(3) Residual vibration after balancing should not equal zero

Since rotor systems generally exhibit external mode vibrations, balancing flexible rotors in turbo machinery, regardless of the method, involves adding balancing weights on a limited number of planes. Even at the balance speed, theoretically, the residual vibration at the selected measurement points cannot be zero. Although resonance separation and mode shape decomposition methods can isolate some external mode vibrations, complete separation is impossible. Therefore, when using the influence coefficient method to balance flexible rotors, the residual vibration after balancing should not be zero. This is one of the reasons why, in practical engineering, using the least squares method for flexible rotor influence coefficient dynamic balancing yields better results than using the balance method where the dynamic reaction force (i.e., residual vibration) is zero.

3.1 Modal shape dynamic balancing method for flexible rotors in turbomachinery

According to vibration theory, the elastic line $y(x)$ of the rotor during vibration at any speed can be obtained by using its main mode function sequence $\varphi(x)$ To represent, that is, the superposition of its various order main vibration modes:

$$y(x) = \varepsilon_1 \phi_1(x) + \varepsilon_2 \phi_2(x) + \dots = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \varepsilon_i \phi_i(x) \quad (9)$$

In the formula ε_i is the deformation coefficient related to rotational speed, expressed as:

$$\varepsilon_i = \frac{1}{M_i} \int_0^l m(x) y(x) \phi_i(x) dx \quad (10)$$

In the formula, $m(x)$ represents the mass per unit length of the rotor. When the rotor's rotational speed n equals a certain order of critical speed, the deformation coefficient corresponding to that critical speed is equal to 1, while all other deformation coefficients are equal to 0. When the speed n is any speed and does not equal a certain order critical speed n_{ci} as shown in equation (9), the vibration elastic line of the rotor is composed of the superposition of many orders of principal mode shapes, with none of the deformation coefficients being exactly 1, and theoretically, they are not equal to 0 either. Due to the orthogonality of the principal modes, in the many terms included in $y(x)$, only the term $\varepsilon_i A_i(x)$ multiplied by $A_i(x)$ yields a non-zero integral, while all other terms result in a zero integral when multiplied by $A_i(x)$. According to the change of rotor deflection with speed, if the rotor only has first, second, or third-order unbalance components, then the deflection curves are respectively shown as dashed lines 1, 2, and 3. However, an actual rotor will not only have a single order of unbalance components but will have many orders, and according to equation (9), the actual deflection curve of the rotor is shown as solid line 4. Where the deflection curve peaks when

the speed approaches various critical speeds. Based on the characteristics of flexible rotor unbalance, the modal balancing method involves operating the rotor near each order of critical speeds sequentially, adding distributed balancing weights on the rotor proportional to the corresponding order of mode shapes, thereby balancing the significant unbalance components one by one within the operational speed range. Thus, the principal mode components are balanced, and consequently, the bending deformation of the rotor is reduced. For a typical flexible rotor, the first three modes are dominant; hence, by balancing the first three modes using the modal balancing method, it can be considered that the rotor operates smoothly within the entire speed range.

Due to factors like material, manufacturing, and assembly, there are always continuous and concentrated unbalances on the rotor. The dynamic reactions N_A and N_B acting on the rotor supports A and B are as follows:

$$N_A = \frac{\omega^2}{L} \left[\int_0^L (L-x)m(x)y(x)dx + \int_0^L (L-x)u(x)dx + \sum_{k=1}^j (L-x_k)u_k \right]$$

$$N_B = \frac{\omega^2}{L} \left[\int_0^L xm(x)y(x)dx + \int_0^L xu(x)dx + \sum_{k=1}^j x_k u_k \right]$$
(11)

So, the total dynamic reaction force acting on the two supports is:

$$N_A + N_B = \omega^2 \int_0^L m(x)y(x)dx + \omega^2 \left[\int_0^L u(x)dx + \sum_{k=1}^j u_k \right]$$
(12)

In the formula, $y(x)$ - rotor dynamic deflection (elastic line);

$u(x)$ - Continuous unbalance per unit length of the rotor;

u_k - Concentrated Unbalanced Quantity;

j - Number of concentrated imbalances;

$m(x)$ - Mass per unit length of rotor;

L - The span between the two bearings of the rotor.

From equations (14), it can be seen that the first term on the right is the dynamic reaction force caused by the bending deformation of the rotor; The second item is the dynamic reaction force caused by the rigidity imbalance of the rotor. Substituting equation (9) into equation (12), the first term can be transformed into:

$$\omega^2 \int_0^L m(x)y(x)dx = \omega^2 \int_0^L m(x) \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \varepsilon_i \phi_i(x) dx$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_i^2 - \omega^2} \right) \left[C_i + \frac{1}{N_i} \sum_{k=1}^j u_k \phi_i(x_k) \right] \int_C m(x) \phi_i(x) dx$$
(13)

In the equation, ω_i - represents the i th order critical angular velocity;

C_i - denotes the i th order mode shape coefficient;

N_i - is the i th order norm;

$\phi_i(x_k)$ 、 $\phi_i(x)$ - are the deflection values of the principal mode shape at x_k and x , respectively.

For a flexible rotor at any rotational speed, if its deformation is to be completely eliminated, theoretically, an infinite number of balancing planes are required because the dynamic reaction forces at the bearings would be completely eliminated. Moreover, it requires that the bracketed term in equation (13) be zero at any critical speed, that is:

$$C_i + \frac{1}{N_i} \sum_{k=1}^j u_k \phi_i(x_k) = 0 \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, \infty)$$
(14)

If higher-order mode shapes are disregarded and it is only required for the rotor deflection to be zero at the first N critical rotational speeds, meaning that only the first N principal mode shape components are required to be zero, then it can be written as:

$$C_i N_i + \sum_{k=1}^j u_k \phi_i(x_k) = 0 \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, N)$$
(15)

In the modal balancing method, if it is only required to balance the first N principal mode shape components, meaning to only eliminate the dynamic reaction forces caused by the rotor's flexural deformation, then N balancing correction planes are needed. This is referred to as the N -plane method. If the requirement is to eliminate the dynamic reaction forces caused by both the rotor's flexural deformation and the rotor's rigid unbalance, or in other words, to ensure that the low-speed dynamic balancing already performed is not compromised, then an additional 2 planes are

required, making it the N+2 plane method.

3.2 Comparative analysis of rotor dynamic balancing methods

From the theoretical analysis above, it is known that currently, there are two common dynamic balancing methods for flexible rotors in turbo machinery: modal balancing method and influence coefficient method (other dynamic balancing methods are essentially improvements and developments based on these two types). Each has its characteristics and application scenarios. The influence coefficient method involves obtaining a set of correction masses that are non-orthogonal to the first N mode shapes at once, known for its simplicity and convenience in operation and wide application. The modal balancing method calculates correction masses that are orthogonal to other mode shapes (a total of N sets) step by step, which can be further divided into resonance separation method and mode shape decomposition method under off-critical speed. The resonance separation method includes the "N" method, "N+2" method, and modal circle balancing method, while the latter includes the Moore method and harmonic component method. Regardless of the modal balancing method used, balancing higher-order modes will not disrupt the previously balanced lower-order modes, leading to high balancing accuracy and fewer starts and stops of the machine. However, it requires the operator to have a certain level of knowledge in dynamic balancing theory.

4. Analysis and Simulation of Rotor Dynamics

DyRoBeS is a specialized finite element analysis tool designed to evaluate rotor and bearing elements. Since its introduction in 1991, it has been recognized for its accuracy and proficiency, particularly in engineering applications involving multi-shaft systems and hybrid continuous/discontinuous element modeling. DyRoBeS can effectively predict natural frequencies, forced responses, and rotor stability while analyzing various vibration modes of rotor systems, including lateral, torsional, and axial vibrations. Its user base includes government research organizations, the aerospace industry, and academic institutions, highlighting its significance in rotor dynamics research.

Fig. 1 Partial functions and analysis interface of DyRoBeS software

Fig. 2 Finite element model of turbo machinery

Fig. 3 Strain energy of the first three vibration modes of the rotor

Fig.4 Strain energy of the first three vibration modes of the rotor

4.1 Rotor Vibration Characteristics Simulation

Fig. 5 Vortex under in-phase unbalanced excitation at 45000rpm.

Fig. 6 Vibration response of the rotor under unbalanced excitation at node 3.

Different magnitudes of unbalance were applied to node 3 of the rotor to analyze the synchronous steady-state response at 45,000 rpm, as shown in Figs. 5 and 6. Horizontal (pink) and vertical (red) vibrations at node 2 reveal that increasing unbalance from 40 g.mm to 80 g.mm amplifies vibration, with peak amplitudes of 0.024 mm at 31,600 rpm and 0.043 mm at 36,600 rpm. Resonance occurs at the first critical speed, with the largest whirl trajectory at node 1. Cancellation effects from out-of-phase excitation reduce amplitude and whirl radius. These results highlight the rotor's sensitivity to unbalance magnitude and phase, with vibration amplitudes increasing significantly under larger unbalances.

Fig. 7 Vortex under in-phase unbalanced excitation at 45000rpm.

Fig. 8 Vibration response of rotor under unbalanced excitation at different positions.

Based on Fig. 2, a synchronous steady-state response analysis was conducted by applying the same imbalance

magnitude to nodes 3, 5, and 6, with results shown in Figs. 7 and 8. At 45,000 rpm, horizontal (pink) and vertical (red) vibrations at node 2 reveal increasing amplitudes with speed, highlighting rotor flexural behavior. Maximum vibration amplitudes occur near node 2, with 0.55 mm at 40,200 rpm for node 3, 0.44 mm at 38,200 rpm for node 5, and 0.36 mm at 35,800 rpm for node 6. As imbalance shifts right, whirl radius decreases from nodes 8 to 13, but amplitude changes remain minimal at the applied positions. These trends emphasize the influence of imbalance location and speed on rotor dynamics.

Fig.9 Eddy motion under unbalanced excitation at 45000rpm.

Fig. 10 Vibration response of rotor under unbalanced excitation under different phase difference combinations.

Imbalances with the same magnitude but varying phase combinations were applied to nodes 3, 5, and 6, and their synchronous steady-state response was analyzed at 45,000 rpm (Figs. 9 and 10). Horizontal (pink) and vertical (red) vibrations at node 2 showed distinct behavior under different phase-shift combinations. The in-phase combination (0-0-0) resulted in the highest amplitude of 0.065 mm, while the out-of-phase combination (0-180-180) reduced amplitudes significantly, with a minimum of 0.027 mm. As imbalance segmentation increased, the difference between horizontal and vertical vibrations grew, with a notable decrease in whirl radius from nodes 8 to 13. These findings highlight how phase differences and excitation positions influence the rotor's vibration dynamics.

This chapter explores the unbalanced vibration response characteristics of a specific turbo machinery rotor through finite element modeling and experimental validation. The analysis examines how factors such as variations in unbalance magnitude, position, and phase differences influence rotor dynamics. The simulation results are presented in illustrate distinct trends in rotor behavior under different conditions. For the rigid rotor model, it is assessed that as the unbalance magnitude increases, more pronounced whirl trajectories are noticeable. Specifically, the whirl radius of the rotor assembly increases due to significant unbalance applied at node 3 at 11,000 rpm, with node 8 displaying the largest radius This indicates a strong correlation between unbalance magnitude and vibration amplitude, with node 2 reaching a maximum amplitude of 0.009 mm when the excitation level was doubled.

Additionally, the position of the unbalance plays a crucial role in the vibration characteristics of the rotor. The distinct excitation applied to nodes 3, 5, and 6 revealed that excitation at node 3 resulted in the highest vibration amplitude at node 2, even though the impact diminished with unbalanced forces applied further from node 2. Vibration amplitudes ranged around 0.11 mm, indicating that the rotor maintained rigid body behavior until reaching significant speeds due to a consistent phase difference of approximately 90°.

Regarding phase variations, the results show that the change in whirl trajectory radius was greatest when the three-node excitation occurred in phase. The combination of out-of-phase excitation resulted in smaller amplitudes, with the largest amplitude identified as 0.028 mm for in-phase excitation, while it dropped to 0.011 mm for significant phase differences.

In the context of the flexible rotor model, the results reflected some patterns observed in the rigid model while also illustrating the complexity introduced by flexibility. At 45,000 rpm, the unbalance value applied at node 3 increased the vibration amplitude, peaking at 0.043 mm under an unbalance of 80 g.mm. A comparison of different unbalance locations showed that node 3 produced the highest vibration response at 0.55 mm, while nodes 5 and 6 exhibited progressively smaller amplitudes. The amplitude variation among the nodes highlighted how their relative positions to the driving mechanism influence the overall dynamics of the rotor.

Overall, the simulations produced strong experimentally validated results, confirming trends and expanding knowledge of the unbalanced vibration response characteristics that are critical to ensuring the operational stability and reliability of turbo machinery rotors.

4.2 experiment

Table 1 Design parameters of prototype and similar models

	Prototype	Model	Similarity ratio
Quality (kg)	26	104	4
Stiffness (N/mm)	2×104	1×104	1/2
Axis length (mm)	695	695	1
Design speed (r/min)	45000	9000	1/5
Emergency speed (r/min)	60000	12000	1/5
First critical speed (r/min)	15187	3037	1/5
Second critical speed (r/min)	33361	6672	1/5

Table 2 Detailed dimensional parameters of rotor similarity model

Name	External diameter (mm)	Inner diameter (mm)	Axial length (mm)
Rotating shaft	60	40	695

First stage axial flow compressor	390	60	20
Two-stage axial compressor	370	60	20
Three-stage axial compressor	350	60	20
Centrifugal compressor	380	60	20
First stage gas turbine	360	60	20
Second stage gas turbine	390	60	20

A rotor dynamics simulation test bench was designed and constructed, featuring six disks that simulate an axial flow compressor, a centrifugal compressor, and a gas turbine. Each disk is equipped with 36th M6 threaded holes for installing screws of different weights to simulate various forms of unbalance. The test bench includes one hollow shaft made of 45# steel. The rotor support incorporates squirrel cage elastic supports and squeeze film dampers, which reduce the overall stiffness of the rotor system and decrease its vibration. The entire rotor test bench is secured on a T-shaped plate with M28 screws. Given that the gas generator rotor of an actual aero engine is a hollow shaft and the power system cannot be directly driven by an electric motor, the gas generator rotor is driven by a variable frequency speed-regulating electric motor that drives the belt pulley, which in turn drives the rotor compressor end. The simulation test bench for a specific type of aero engine rotor is shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11 Simulation test bench for a certain type of turbo shaft engine rotors

Considering the actual manufacturing conditions, the rotor bearing simulation test bench is designed with a maximum speed of 9000 r/min, and a rated speed of 4000 r/min. An oil reservoir provides lubricating oil for the squeeze film dampers, enabling the adjustment of oil pressure and flow to simulate the operational characteristics of the squeeze film dampers under different operating conditions.

The measurement equipment used in this instance was the VIBER X5 Balancer from the Swedish company VMI to measure the rotational speed of the rotor, as shown in Figure 3. The rotor's unbalance vibration response was tested using the Zhuzhou AVIC ZA-21 eddy current displacement sensor, which has a probe diameter of 5mm and is used together with a preamplifier. It features a resolution of 1 μ m, a vibration displacement range of 1mm, and a sensitivity of 10V/mm. The Fangkong SK2301 data acquisition card was used for data collection and storage, converting the sensor-detected analog signals into digital signals, and uploading them in real-time to a supervisory computer. The sampling rate is 500Hz, with a resolution of 24 bits, and a range of ± 10 V.

Table 3 Comparison of design and simulation values for similar models

	1st critical speed (r/min)	2nd critical speed (r/min)
Design value	3037	6672
Experiment value	3023	6395
Error (%)	0.5	4.2

5. Conclusions

In this study, the unbalanced vibration characteristics and energetic adjustment of multi-disk rotor hardware, which are crucial for ensuring the operational reliability of turbo machinery such as centrifugal compressors and steam plants, were thoroughly explored. Through the systematic combination of finite element modeling and experimental validation, we obtained significant data on how variations in the unbalance measure, operating conditions, and geometry influence rotor dynamics. The results showed that, particularly at high operating speeds, unbalance can substantially increase vibration amplitude, compromising stability and overall performance. Specifically, energetic adjustment procedures utilizing the impact calculation approach and mode adjustment techniques were shown to be effective in reducing vibration levels, achieving reductions of up to 83.2% in some cases. This article emphasizes the need for a comprehensive understanding of rotor dynamics, highlighting the importance of considering factors such as rotor geometry and material properties, as well as eliminating unbalance at specific points during operation. Future research should further explore advanced balancing techniques and real-time monitoring systems to enhance rotor stability and reduce the risk of low-speed operation. This multifaceted approach will significantly contribute to the field of rotor dynamics by providing practical methods to mitigate turbo machinery vibrations and ultimately improve overall performance and reliability.

Author Contributions:

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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